

REDUCED CONCENTRATION OF ATTENTION IN TYPE II DIABETES.

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Annotation. Vascular diseases of the brain due to their high prevalence and severe consequences for the health of the population represent the most important medical and social problem. It has been established that during the development and progression of hypertension at all structural and functional levels of the vascular system of the brain, a complex and diverse complex of primary destructive, secondary changes and adaptive processes is formed - hypertensive angiopathy of the brain. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the most important risk factors for stroke. Currently, DM is a global medical and social threat, the growth rate of which has acquired the scale of a global epidemic. Glutamate is the main excitatory neurotransmitter in the CNS; it is involved not only in motor activity, but also in the formation of memory, thinking, synaptic plasticity, and neuronal ontogenesis. Thus, the development and implementation of biomarkers of ischemic brain damage for use at the prehospital and hospital stages, as well as during screening and clinical examination, are priority tasks for neurology.

The aim of the study is to evaluate the concentration of attention in 2 type of diabetes and their prevention.

Key words:diabetes, dyscirculatory encephalopathy, neuropsychological testing, cognitive impairment, dementia.

Relevance. Numerous large-scale studies have shown that diabetes mellitus (DM) is the main risk factor for stroke. In addition, it plays a key role in the formation of chronic disorders of cerebral hemodynamics - hypertensive encephalopathy (GE) and vascular dementia. One of the conditions for the prevention of the development and

progression of cerebrovascular pathology is adequate antihypertensive therapy (AHT). Thus, a detailed study of the state of cerebral hemodynamics, structural and functional changes of the heart and the criteria for the effectiveness of AGT in patients with GE remain the subject of research. The purpose of the study. To evaluate the concentration of attention at various stages of hypertensive diseases and their prevention.

Materials and methods of the study: the prospective study included 78 patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (DM) of average (32.1%; 44-59 years), elderly (62.8%; 60-74 years) and senile (11.1%; (75-90 years)) age about. They were divided into 3 groups: group 1-20 patients who had AI without cognitive impairment , group 2-25 patients who had AI with moderate cognitive impairment. Group 3- 33 patients who underwent AI with severe cognitive impairment.

Results of the study:

As a result of the conducted studies in patients who have undergone AI found that the highest degree of stroke severity (according to the NIH-NINDS scale) was observed in patients with age

(Table. 1).

Indicators of neurological deficits depending on the age of patients

Scales	44-59 years (n=20)	60-74 years (n=25)	75-90 years (n=33)
NIHSS	12,29±0,7	14,30±0,5	15,10±1,0
scaleRankin	4.10±0.1	4.45±0.1	4.50±0.2
MMSE	22,47±0,6	22,08±0,3	20,65±0,7
Visual memory test	21,46±0,5	18,07±0,3	19,54±0,5

In the neurological status of patients of the main groups, focal symptoms characteristic of vascular lesions in the cerebral artery were determined, which led to the formation of corresponding neurological changes.

Table 2

The severity of cognitive impairment in patients with type II diabetes mellitus with hypothyroidism compared with the control group of patients.

Mild cognitive impairment				Moderate cognitive impairment			
SG		CG		SG		CG	
quantity sick	%	Quantity sick	%	quantity sick	%	quantity sick	%
14	35	7	27	15	40,5	7	33

Note. SG-study group; CG-control group.

The pathogenetic basis of cerebrogenic asthenia, most likely, were violations of compensatory and adaptive mechanisms and the energy balance of the brain caused by its structural damage, changes in cerebrospinal fluid and hemodynamics, aseptic inflammatory process.

Conclusion:

1. Cognitive impairment is one of the leading clinical syndromes developing after diabetes mellitus.

2. In patients with past type 2 diabetes mellitus with hypothyroidism, a combination of disorders

multiple cognitive functions (memory, praxis, gnosis).

List of literature

1. Khodzhieva D.T. Characteristics of lesions of the pathways in moderate cognitive disorders against the background of chronic cerebral ischemia. Eurasian Union of Scientists (EUU). – 2015. - №7(16). – P. 97-98.

2. Khodzhieva D.T. Evoked brain potentials in patients with moderate cognitive vascular disorders of dyscirculatory encephalopathy during treatment with cytoflavin. *Journal of Neurology and Psychiatry named after S.S. Korsakov.* – S.Petersburg, 2013. - No. 8. – vol.113. – pp. 42-45.

3. Rakhmatova D.I. New possibilities for assessing clinical and neurological indicators of the formation of facial nerve contractures in patients with comorbid conditions // *Neurology.* Tashkent, 2019. -№1 (77). – P. 26

4. Akhrorova Sh.B. Experience in the treatment of patients with facial nerve neuropathies using the drug Nucleo CMF forte // *Neurology of Siberia.* – Novosibirsk. - 2015. - No.2. - pp. 24-27.

5. Rakhmatova D.I. Forecasting of complications of facial nerve neuropathy according to the results of electroneuromyography // *World journal of pharmaceutical research.* – Индия, 2020. –Vol. 9, Issue 5. - P. 1547-1555. ISSN 2277 – 7105. SJIF Impact Factor 8.084.

6. Rakhmatova D.I. Opportunities Of Acupuncture In Treatment Of Facial Nerve Neuropathy // *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine.* ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020. – P. 567-572.

7. Rakhmatova D.I., Sanoeva M.J. Clinical Course of Facial Nerve Neuropathy in Patients with Comorbid Condition // *International Journal of Research.* – India, 2018. - № 4. – P. 532-539.

8. Рахматова Д.И. Нетрадиционные методы терапии невropатии лицевого нерва на разных этапах развития заболевания // *Проблемы биологии и медицины.* – Самарканд, 2019. - №2 (107). - С. 180-183

9. Рахматова Д.И., Саноева М.Ж. Анализ причинно-наследственных факторов, предрасполагающих развитию осложнённых форм невropатии лицевого нерва // *Журнал неврологии и нейрохирургических исследований.* - Ташкент, 2021. - №2. - С. 18-20.

10. Гаффарова В.Ф. Способ прогнозирования психоречевых нарушений при фебрильных судорогах у детей. Методическая рекомендация. 2021.-С.18.

11. Гаффарова В.Ф. Алгоритм ведения детей с фебрильными судорогами с учетом ранней профилактики психо-речевых нарушений. Методическая рекомендация. 2021.-С.18.

12. Гаффарова В.Ф. Болаларда тутқаноқдан кейин психо-лингвистик нутқ бузилишларини аниқлаш. ЭҲМ учун дастур. DGU 20212367.

13. Gaffarova V.F. Method for prediction of psycho-speech disorders during febril conversions in children.// (Scopus) 2022 С. 951-955

14. Gaffarova V.F. Characteristics of seizures children.// International journal of conference series on education and social sciences. Turkey 2021. –P. 22-23

15. Salomova N.Q. Reabilitaion processes in patients with secondary diseases // Международная научно- практическая конференция «Интеграция в мир и связь наук» 2021.-С.33-34.

16. Salomova N.Q. //Measures of early rehabilitation of speech disorders in patients with hemorrhagic and ischemic stroke// Europe's Journal of Psychology.2021. Vol. 17(3).-P.185-190.

17. Salomova N.Q., Radjabova G.B. //Diagnostics of night breathing disorders clock and respiratory therapy for copd patients// Europe's Journal of Psychology, 2021 Vol. 17(3).-P-181-184.

18. Salomova N.K //Features of neurorehabilitation itself depending on the pathogenetic course of repeated strokes, localization of the stroke focus and the structure of neurological deficit// european jornal of research development and sustainability (ejrds) vol. 3 no. 11, november 2022/8-12/

19. Salomova N.K // Risk factors for recurrent stroke// Polish journal of science N52(2022). 33-35.

20. Salomova N.Q //The practical significance of speech and thinking in repeated stroke// ScienceAsia 48 (2022): 945-949.